

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PSYCHOSOCIAL DYNAMICS OF YOUTH

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Abstract

Adolescence is an important stage in the psychological, social and biological development of a person. During this age period, the main qualities of personality are formed, self-awareness, self-consciousness, self-esteem and moral qualities develop. Young people's social relationships, friendships and inter-gender interactions are strengthened, and social activity increases. Independent decision-making and the desire to participate in various areas of life are more pronounced during this period. The management of emotions, ideal love and sexual maturation processes are also of particular importance during adolescence. Parents' adherence to the principles of freedom, support and consultation in their relationships with young people contributes to the correct formation of personality. The article also emphasizes the gender differences in the socio-psychological development of young people and their attitudes to values in modern times.

Keywords: adolescence, personality development, self-awareness, self-consciousness, gender relations, ideal love, parental relationship

A person goes through different age periods in his development, and each period has a certain impact on the development of personality. The youth of a person's life is the period of physical maturity, the rapid development of his self-awareness, intellect, the formation of his unique high qualities, worldview, choosing a profession and starting an old age. The youth age in its development usually goes through two stages: the first stage is called early youth (15-17 years old), and the second stage is called mature youth (18-25 years old).

Early youth is a period when the basic qualities of personality are formed and social activity increases. He gains citizenship and the right to be elected. At this age, a number of new qualities emerge: self-awareness, self-esteem and self-consciousness develop; moral views and beliefs, worldviews are formed; the tendency to independence, self-affirmation and self-education strengthens, etc.

“During adolescence, a number of socio-psychological qualities of personality, especially idealism, moral purity, spiritual richness, activity, being principled in work, consistency of words and deeds, clarity of purpose, etc., become more noticeable and rapidly form. At the same time, they engage in the struggle for ideas and beliefs, and defend their worldviews” [4, p.189].

Young people have a strong need for reflection on their feelings and thoughts, for self-awareness. Questions such as “Who am I?”, “What am I capable of?”, “What is the meaning of life?” make them think. At this age, interest in moral issues also increases. Speaking the truth, being principled, and honest are characteristic of young people. They value honesty, humility, hard work, simplicity, and kindness in people more highly. Criticism and self-criticism are characteristic of young people.

Youth is a period of searching for vital innovations and adventures. The end of the youth period means the existence of a generation fully prepared for society. For this reason, parents who want to correct any mistakes in the behavior of young people should do the process

indirectly, not directly, and prefer a friendly, companionship position. In order for young people to understand their personal needs and feelings, to be responsible for the steps they take, and to make important life decisions independently, parents should accept that they are growing up, give their children who have entered the youth period freedom, and try to help them as advisors, not as executors, in overcoming the difficulties they encounter. It is not necessary to think that if young people are given freedom, their attachment to the family will decrease, on the contrary, the value of the family will be recognized more. Because, the feeling of freedom and making independent decisions naturally cause certain difficulties for young people, and as each difficulty is experienced, the value of the parents who solve these difficulties on their own is also recognized and their hard work is also appreciated.

“Young people develop and are formed under the influence of biological, psychological, psychosexual and sociological factors. Although biological development is completed in the body during youth, psychological (cognitive processes, worldview, beliefs, will and moral qualities, feelings, etc.), psychosexual (formation of interest in the opposite sex, tendencies, needs, etc.), sociological (integration into social relations, formation of social status and position, etc.) development becomes more active and improved. Among these, socio-psychological factors occupy a special place in the formation of young people as a personality. Therefore, youth can be noted as a socio-psychological phenomenon” [2, p.341].

“A number of psychologists have called the early youth period by different names. For example, Russian psychologist L.S. Vygotsky characterized this age stage as the puberty age period, and D.B. Elkonin as the period of older adolescence. L.I. Bojovich believed that the most important feature of mental development during the older school age period is the realization of self-determination, opportunities and aspirations in human society. During the older school age period, the contradiction between the mental capabilities of young

people and the increasing demands of the elderly and society becomes the driving force of mental development" [1, p.307].

The youth period is considered a continuation of education, a period of improvement of personal qualities formed up to this time. This period is the culmination of the formation of female and male characteristics, the foundation of which has been laid since childhood, and is the period when the foundation of a worldview specific to women and men for later life is laid. During this period, young people already make their independent choices based on stereotypes and standards about femininity and masculinity and demonstrate behavior in accordance with their gender in mutual relations. Young people who have graduated from high school and earned the title of student try to master existing knowledge related to socio-political, scientific, economic, cultural, religious, etc. fields. The set of these components serves to improve a person's worldview.

During the youth period, the process of mastering the secrets of the chosen professions, the formation of independent ideas in accordance with the needs of life and the struggle for the realization of these ideas, neutrality or choice between the social, real and ideal self in order to gain appropriate respect in society, the prominence of the differential sexual behavior characteristic of women and men, and the change of the structure of the personality in accordance with social relations take place. The joining of young boys and girls to existing relationships leads to the loss of character traits preserved from childhood, and the emergence of relationships similar to the relationships existing between adults, both internally and externally. If the basis of these relationships is mutual respect and equality, the subsequent process leads to a positive direction of the social lifestyle and inter-gender relations.

The establishment of youth friendships and attempts to enter into closer interpersonal relationships with people occur in girls 1.5-2 years earlier than in boys. This is due to the somewhat earlier onset of puberty in girls, and this need is felt in them much earlier than in boys. In late adolescence and early adulthood, they tend to be friends with representatives of the opposite sex. Girls, as a rule (unlike boys), attach more importance to building interpersonal relationships with people of the same age group and are more emotional.

During adolescence, the mechanism for managing emotions becomes active, but emotionality is often observed in young people's behavior in response to the difficulties of adapting to numerous social innovations.

One of the biggest changes in the emotional world of young people is the feeling of love. Psychologists associate it with sexual maturation. In terms of its content, it differs significantly from the sympathy of younger schoolchildren and the first love of adolescents. While in adolescents the feeling of love, which arises on the basis of sympathy for the opposite sex, has a superficial, attractive character, in early youth this feeling is distinguished by its depth, strength and true love. Since sexual maturation is completed at

this age, it is characterized by clearly expressed sexual overtones.

During this period, young people's search for the ideal lover in their impressions in real life and some young men or women, even if they start a family, are driven to spiritual loneliness due to the failure of this search. Young people who have experienced the conflicting period of adolescence often understand the correctness of parental advice better during this period, believe that it will be beneficial for them, and their trust in parents and teachers increases. Representatives of the younger generation must be able to choose between good and evil while still under parental care. The closer the parents or people who will support them are to those they protect, the less danger awaits that person.

Youth is a period of education and upbringing in which a person has the authority to form the necessary qualities in himself by passing ethical and aesthetic moral rules through his mental framework and to implement them without accepting any interference. Youth is the period of laying the foundation for determining the social status of the individual, the enrichment of rights and duties, the beginning of independent activity and social activism.

"The processes that accelerate during adolescence include cognitive processes, voluntary regulation of emotion, socialization, assimilation of social rules and adherence to them, self-affirmation, improvement of worldview, psychological development, political and critical thinking, learning of legal and social rules, exercise of citizenship rights, manifestation of gender-specific characteristics in behavior, the need to be loved and chosen, acquisition of sexual culture, inclination to start a family, formation of an individual lifestyle, ambition, struggle for the realization of dreams, acquisition of the secrets of the necessary qualifications to occupy a worthy place in the business environment, integration into the labor market, independence in personal and business activities" [3, p.141].

The period of youth is an important stage in the development of the growing generation - the completion of the transition to adulthood, the formation of self-awareness, and the formation of a socio-psychological being. The formation of social qualities accelerates during the youth period. As young people develop, they fully understand their goals and strive to achieve them, which has an impact on the perfection of their personality.

During adolescence, personality is formed as a biosocial-psychological entity, where enterprising, principled, responsible forms of behavior are formed; the young person becomes ready to perform complex intellectual operations, his special abilities develop rapidly. Communication and the creation of friendship groups of young people appear as their natural, socio-psychological need. At this age, the main educational aspect of the communication process is more noticeable, they strive to unite with their peers, create friendship groups, and of course, in this process, interpersonal relationships, friendship, and comradeship are formed in young people.

Thanks to the development of self-awareness, which is an important psychological phenomenon in

adolescence, the young person begins to better understand his personality, abilities, moral qualities, himself, evaluates his place and position in the group, is able to see his positive and negative aspects, then the concept of the self becomes more stable, self-control, self-determination are formed. Young people are assessed by those around them (relatives, neighbors, parents) as old people in terms of both physical and mental qualities, the feeling and tendency of old age in them is combined with the act of self-affirmation, and they try to stand out from the elderly, to show themselves in a more independent, original way. During this period, in addition to understanding and evaluating their psychological qualities, the content of their self-consciousness, their self-image changes: boys and girls become excessively obsessed with themselves, appreciate their external beauty, a small physical defect worries them, and even if boys are very fat or short, they consider it a defect for themselves. Young people use physiognomic masks to hide their appearance flaws, even certain deformities. Young people explain their personal moral qualities, as well as their behavior, manners and attitude, their external beauty, their mind from a socio-social perspective and evaluate them as a whole, and they also understand the values of outsiders. However, when older schoolchildren do not evaluate themselves realistically, they are at risk of egocentrism. Young people's self-awareness depends largely on their social background, level of education, personal characteristics, the people around them, and the copies of the works they read. Young people make certain judgments about themselves based on these factors. The self-esteem that boys and girls give to themselves during adolescence and the evaluation of others form and develop a sense of personal dignity and self-respect in them. The main feature characterizing the self-esteem of young people is the understanding of sexual characteristics and qualities. The social activity and life position of young people have strategic importance and are characterized by orientation towards the future. Young people are not just interested in domestic and international events, they think about their short and long-term plans. Young people, while understanding the outside world, evaluate it, express their attitude to the world, and defend their own particular views, beliefs, opinions, and attitudes.

The correct implementation of gender roles is one of the essential conditions for the formation of normal relationships. Because the success of both the family and the business sphere depends on the correct distribution and implementation of these roles. The interdependence between representatives of the opposite sex inevitably leads to the establishment of healthy relationships. The closer people get to know each other, the more independent and liberated their relationships become. Mutual need makes representatives of the opposite sex observe each other's positive or negative characteristics. Both women and men are looking for a real image of a person who is in harmony with their nature in order to find their life partner. If this finding coincides with the image existing in the dream, then processes such as supporting, helping, and understanding each other will

continue until the end of their lives. Therefore, such a process also has a positive effect on behavior. Thus, the imagination of ideal female-male images plays the role of a moral regulator for the behavior of young boys and girls, characterizing the determination of their relationships with their peers of the opposite sex.

Unfortunately, often when searching for the imaginary image of the desired partner for family life, the matching of external similarity overshadows the verification of the matching process of spiritual similarity. When family life is established, the problems associated with the lack of spiritual compatibility outweigh the satisfaction of the life partner in terms of external appearance. This leads to an increase in the number of unsuccessful families.

Boys are more concerned with accuracy in any matter. Girls, on the other hand, are more prone to romance, approach life through an emotional prism, are more prone to emotional reactions, and are more sensitive.

Since adolescence is considered the most popular period for boys to choose girls for marriage, girls strive to succeed in interpersonal relationships, attract the attention of others, and be liked. Young girls who like to be the center of attention, as well as trying to be liked by demonstrating qualities such as politeness, gentleness, and good-naturedness, are more sociable (this process also has a certain connection with biological development: girls speak faster than boys, walk faster, and the early development and fluency of girls' oral speech, the natural ability to follow the speech of others, their deep interest in people, and their deep, close communication with their mothers ensure the development of their speech organs and sociability). In young boys, the reason why the level of courage, organization, awareness, collectivism, solidarity and other volitional characteristics is more developed than other characteristics is explained by the high physiological capabilities of boys, for example: the ability to defend the interests of their friends through force has a positive effect on the formation of qualities such as collectivism, courage, ambition, organization. Therefore, although young boys and girls have similar general characteristics in their personalities, their differences due to their gender also attract attention: Young boys have higher levels of willpower qualities such as organization, determination, persistence, hard work, courage, initiative, solidarity, and keeping one's word compared to other characteristics, while young girls have higher levels of moral qualities such as responsibility, sociability, and shyness, and lower levels of willpower qualities such as organization, determination, persistence, hard work, courage, initiative, and keeping one's word.

As young people's ability to think independently improves, they give a more objective assessment of their parents' personal qualities. Therefore, it should be taken for granted that a young person, despite loving and respecting their parents, does not choose their parents as a role model for themselves due to their personal qualities. In such a case, instead of being offended, the parent should take another look at their own personal qualities. Parents should realize that if

children were more inclined to observe and imitate until adolescence, they already demonstrate and apply what they have acquired during adolescence. If a parent does not like something in the behavior of their young child, they should correctly determine what the mistakes made are in time and analyze in detail the ways that will serve to eliminate this problem. Because, direct educational influences during this period can cause conflicts.

The rules that help parents establish normal relationships with their adolescent children include: respecting the child's personal qualities; creating conditions for self-affirmation; providing freedom of thought; consulting with the child in making family decisions; setting a personal example in guiding the process of forming the qualities necessary for adulthood; providing freedom of communication and activity; providing assistance in determining an individual lifestyle; showing confidence in the young person's ambition; approaching failures with support, not criticism; not interfering in the young person's intimate life; resolving any misunderstandings not through conflict, but through ways based on mutual understanding; accepting the young person's independence.

Every person who thinks about his future works out methods of transferring his life experience, which he has improved over time, to the younger generation and fights to prevent the mistakes made from being repeated again. The successful result of the struggle is manifested in the formation of a high-level personality for society. If any era supported an authoritarian position in upbringing, now violent upbringing methods are categorically not accepted. The new era changes the positive and negative features of the past in accordance with current needs. This process also has an

analogous effect on the dynamics of the development of the personality of the younger generation: young people's views on values, lifestyles, desires, deeds, etc. change. If in the past, the majority of young people preferred romance, today's young people live more realistically and act in accordance with democratic principles. In this context, the acquisition of universal moral values, comprehensive provision of human rights, and the creation of sound material and spiritual foundations in the formation of the younger generation are considered to be the most urgent problems of the modern era.

The life process can also be viewed as a process of confrontation, where conflict-causing factors, unfavorable conditions, and obstacles confront a person and either destroy or educate him in this confrontation. From this perspective, the correct approach of parents to their young children: their readiness to help in any difficulty, their efforts to make their lives more interesting, and their efforts to educate their moral and volitional qualities at the appropriate level ensure the problem-free youth of the growing generation and the formation of normal personalities of the people who will form the composition of society.

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